

STUDIES IN FRIEDEL-CRAFTS' ACYLATION. PART II. ACYLATION OF ACETOTOLUIDIDES AND ACETANILIDE

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Friedel-Crafts' acylation of acetanilide, aceto-*m*-toluidide and aceto-*p*-toluidide has been investigated using several acyl chlorides. Acetanilide and aceto-*m*-toluidide afforded the corresponding *p*-aminoketones, and in case of aceto-*p*-toluidide, the condensation failed

The work described in this paper is an extension of our previous communication (Sacha and Patel, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 129).

Kunckell (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1912, I, 136) reported that Friedel-Crafts' acylation of aceto-*m*-toluidide with chloroacetyl chloride effected substitution, *para* with respect to the amino group. In this paper Friedel-Crafts' acylation of aceto-*m*-toluidide has been reported with other acyl halides and substitution has been found to occur in a similar position, e.g., with acetyl chloride, 4-acetamino-2-methylacetophenone (I) was obtained in good yield. This successful condensation is contrary to the observation made by Kunckell (*Ber. deut. Pharm. Ges.*, 1911, 21, 419) that the Friedel-Crafts condensation of an anilide derivative would succeed only if the acyl halide is halogenated or its boiling point exceeds 90°. This as well as other condensations reported in this paper has been carried out by heating an anilide derivative, acyl halide and finely powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride in proportions of 1 : 1 : 3 respectively.

The constitution assigned to (I) has been confirmed by hydrolysing it to the corresponding amino-ketone (II), followed by replacement of the amino group by the hydroxy group on adding the diazotised solution of (II) to a boiling H₂SO₄ solution, and proving the identity of the product obtained, viz., 4-hydroxy-2-methylacetophenone, with the known authentic sample obtained on the Fries rearrangement of *m*-cresyl acetate (Skraup and Poller, *Ber.*, 1924, 57, 2033). In a similar manner the Friedel-Crafts acylation of aceto-*m*-toluidide with benzoyl chloride, *o*-chlorobenzoyl chloride and *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride has been carried out successfully, and in each case *p*-substitution occurs.

Friedel-Crafts' acylation of acetanilide with benzoyl chloride furnished *p*-aminobenzophenone in 7% yield (vide Baeyer and Villiger, *Ber.*, 1904, 37, 605, who obtained it on reduction of *p*-nitrobenzophenone). Similarly, on condensation of acetanilide with *o*-chlorobenzoyl chloride and *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride, 4-acetamino-2'-chlorobenzophenone (III) and 4-acetamino-4'-nitrobenzophenone were obtained respectively in about 20% and 24% yields. In the previous communication (*loc. cit.*) Friedel-Crafts' acetylation of acetanilide (yield 19%) has been reported. It is interesting to note that acetanilide, which affords on nitration, halogenation etc. the corresponding reaction products in excellent yields, affords the amino-ketones in poor yields on its Friedel-Crafts' acylation.

The free base of (III), viz, 4-amino-2'-chlorobenzophenone (IV), has been reported in literature as a product of indefinite constitution (Montagne, *Ber.*, 1916, 49, 2251) as the author obtained it on reduction of 4-nitro-2'(?)-chlorobenzophenone (V) which he obtained as one of the products of Friedel-Crafts' acylation of chlorobenzene with *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride. The identity of (IV) with the product obtained by Montagne confirms the constitution assigned by him to (V).

We have studied the acylation of aceto-*p*-toluidide with both acetyl chloride and benzoyl chloride under different sets of experimental conditions, with and without solvents like acetylene tetrachloride and carbon disulphide, and taking different proportions of the reactants, particularly using a very large excess of anhydrous aluminium chloride; but in each case the reaction failed. Kunckell (*Ber.*, 1900, 33, 2644) has reported that Friedel-Crafts' acylation of aceto-*p*-toluidide with chloroacetyl chloride affords two products, in one the substitution is *ortho* with respect to the amino group while in the other it is *ortho* with respect to the methyl group. We therefore repeated the work of Kunckell and confirmed his results. Friedel-Crafts' acylation of an anilide derivative leading to *ortho*-substitution with respect to the amino group is rare. The only other instance of this type reported so far is Friedel-Crafts' acylation of 4-acetamino-1:2-dimethylbenzene with chloroacetyl chloride (Kunckell and Schneider, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1912, 86, 429).

EXPERIMENTAL

Friedel-Crafts' Acylation of Aceto-*m*-toluidide

*Acetylation of Aceto-*m*-toluidide to 2-Methyl-4-acetaminoacetophenone.*—To an ice-cooled mixture of aceto-*m*-toluidide (10 g.) and finely powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (30 g.) acetyl chloride (10 g.) was added in small lots. The reaction mixture after being kept for half an hour at room temperature was heated on a water-bath for 2 hours and decomposed with ice and HCl, when 2-methyl-4-acetaminoacetophenone separated out as a faint yellow solid. It crystallised from hot water as colorless long needles, m. p. 138-39°, yield 5.5 g. (Found: N, 7.4. $_{11}H_{13}O_2N$ requires N, 7.3 per cent).

2-Methyl-4-aminoacetophenone.—The above acetamino-ketone was hydrolysed by heating it with an excess of dilute HCl on a boiling water-bath. The product obtained crystallised from petrol in pale brown small needles, m. p. 95-96°. (Found: N, 9.5. $C_9H_{11}ON$ requires N, 9.4 per cent).

2-Methyl-4-acetaminobenzoic Acid.—2-Methyl-4-acetaminoacetophenone (2 g.) was oxidised by heating it with 4% $KMnO_4$ solution (200 c.c.) and magnesium sulphate (8 g.). The colorless solution, obtained on filtration of the hot reaction mixture, after concentration was acidified. The product obtained crystallised from boiling water in colorless, shining, small needles, m. p. 222° (decomp.). (Found: N, 7.6; equiv., 195.8. $C_{10}H_{11}O_3N$ requires N, 7.2 per cent. Equiv., 193.0). Kunckell (*loc. cit.*) has reported the melting point as 243°. As the melting points did not agree, the constitution assigned to the above amino-ketone had to be proved by another method shown below.

2-Methyl-4-hydroxyacetophenone (p-acetyl-m-cresol).—2-Methyl-4-aminoacetophenone (2.0 g.) was dissolved in hot 50% solution of H_2SO_4 (10 c.c.) and cooled below 5° . It was then diazotised with sodium nitrite solution (1.0 g. in 3 c.c. water). The diazotised solution was added in small lots to a well-stirred, boiling 50% solution of H_2SO_4 (20 c.c.). The brown solid, which separated out on cooling, crystallised from boiling water as faint brown scales, m. p. $130-31^\circ$. It was found to be identical with *p*-acetyl-*m*-cresol obtained as one of the products (non-volatile) on the Fries rearrangement of *m*-cresyl acetate (Skraup and Poller, *loc. cit.*), mixed m. p. remaining undepressed.

Benzoylation of Aceto-m-toluidide to 2-Methyl-4-aminobenzophenone.—The reaction was carried out as indicated above, using benzoyl chloride, the quantities of the reactants remaining the same. The product obtained on decomposition of the reaction mixture with ice and HCl after treatment with dilute bicarbonate solution and final washing with cold water remained pasty even on keeping for a long time. It was therefore hydrolysed to 2-methyl-4-aminobenzophenone which crystallised from benzene as yellowish needles, m. p. 141° , yield 10 g. (Found: N, 6.2. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{13}ON$: N, 6.6 per cent).

2-Methyl-4-hydroxybenzophenone (p-Benzoyl-m-cresol).—The above amino-ketone was diazotised as indicated before and the diazotised solution was gradually heated to 50° on a water-bath, and kept at that temperature for about 15 minutes. The pasty mass obtained on cooling was extracted with dilute NaOH solution. The clear alkali extract was acidified when an oily substance was obtained which on long standing solidified. It crystallised from benzene in small needles, m. p. $128-29^\circ$. It was found to be identical with *p*-benzoyl-*m*-cresol, obtained as one of the products (non-volatile) on the Fries rearrangement of *m*-cresyl benzoate (Heller, *Ber.*, 1913, 46, 1503); mixed m.p. remained undepressed. *N-Acetyl derivative*, obtained by heating 2-methyl-4-aminobenzophenone with an excess of acetic anhydride, crystallised from petrol-ether as yellowish white thin plates, m.p. $128-29^\circ$. (Found: N, 5.3. $C_{16}H_{15}O_2N$ requires N, 4.4 per cent).

Acylation of Aceto-m-toluidide using o-Chlorobenzoyl Chloride to 2-Methyl-4-amino-2'-chlorobenzophenone.—The pasty condensation product, obtained by carrying out the reaction as above, was hydrolysed with hot HCl (conc.) and the product obtained crystallised from boiling water as thin yellowish needles, m. p. $98-100^\circ$, yield 4 g. (Found: N, 5.5; Cl, 14.6. $C_{14}H_{12}ONCl$ requires N, 5.7; Cl, 14.4 per cent).

Acylation of Aceto-m-toluidide using p-Nitrobenzoyl Chloride to 2-Methyl-4-amino-4'-nitrobenzophenone.—The condensation was carried out as indicated above and as the product obtained did not solidify, it was hydrolysed to the amino-ketone which crystallised from benzene as dirty yellow granules, m.p. $149-52^\circ$, yield 7 g. (Found: N, 9.5. $C_{15}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires N, 9.4 per cent).

N-Acetyl derivative of 2-methyl-4-amino-4'-nitrobenzophenone crystallised from acetone and petrol-ether mixture as pale yellow granules, m. p. $159-61^\circ$. (Found: N, 10.7. $C_{16}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 10.9 per cent).

Friedel-Crafts' Acylation of Acetanilide

Benzoylation of Acetanilide to p-Aminobenzophenone.—The condensation of acetanilide with benzoyl chloride was effected by the method described above. The amino-ketone obtained on hydrolysis of the condensation product crystallised from boiling water as small pinkish white needles, m. p. 124°, yield 1 g. (Found: N, 6.8. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{11}ON$: N, 7.1 per cent). Baeyer and Villiger (*loc. cit.*), who obtained it on reduction of *p*-nitrobenzophenone, recorded the same m. p.

Acylation of Acetanilide with p-Chlorobenzoyl Chloride to 4-Acetamino-2'-chlorobenzophenone.—The product, obtained by the method described above after washing with dilute bicarbonate solution and finally with water, crystallised from boiling water in thin pinkish plates, m. p. 145-47°, yield 4 g. (Found: N, 5.2; Cl, 12.8. $C_{15}H_{12}O_2NCl$ requires N, 5.1; Cl, 13.0 per cent).

4-Amino-2'-chlorobenzophenone, obtained on hydrolysis of the above acetamino-ketone, crystallised from boiling water in small thin needles, m. p. 112°. (Found: N, 5.8; Cl, 15.2. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{10}ONCl$: N, 6.0; Cl, 15.3 per cent). Montagne (*loc. cit.*) records the same m. p.

N-Benzoyl derivative, obtained by treating 4-amino-2'-chlorobenzophenone with an excess of benzoyl chloride in presence of alkali solution, crystallised from acetone and petrol-ether mixture as dirty yellowish powder, m. p. 132-34°. (Found: N, 4.2; Cl, 10.7. $C_{20}H_{14}O_2NCl$ requires N, 4.1; Cl, 10.6 per cent).

Acylation of Acetanilide with p-Nitrobenzoyl Chloride to 4-Acetamino-4'-nitrobenzophenone.—The product obtained by the method described above, after washing with dilute bicarbonate solution and subsequently with water, crystallised from acetone and petrol-ether mixture as a pale yellow powder, m. p. 194-95°, yield 5 g. (Found: N, 9.7. $C_{15}H_{13}O_4N_2$ requires N, 9.9 per cent).

4-Amino-4'-nitrobenzophenone, obtained on hydrolysis of the above acetamino-ketone, crystallised from acetone as a yellow powder, m. p. 180-81°. (Found: N, 11.7. $C_{13}H_{10}O_3N_2$ requires N, 11.6 per cent).

N-Benzoyl derivative of the above amino-ketone crystallised from acetone and petrol-ether mixture as a yellowish powder, m. p. 199-200°. (Found: N, 7.9. $C_{20}H_{14}O_4N_2$ requires N, 8.1 per cent).

Friedel-Crafts' Acylation of Aceto-p-toluidide

The condensation of aceto-*p*-toluidide with both acetyl chloride and benzoyl chloride was attempted under different experimental conditions mentioned in the theoretical; but in each case the reaction failed and the aceto-*p*-toluidide was recovered unchanged.